

OPTIMIZATION OF BIOGAS PRODUCTION FROM C3, C4, AND CAM PLANTS: A CASE STUDY OF WATER HYACINTH, SUGARCANE, AND CACTUS PLANTS.

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Abstract

The ever-increasing need for alternative energy sources has driven researchers to study ways through which renewable sources of energy can sustain the high energy demand. When substrates that produce the least quantity and quality of biogas are relied on, there is too much use of energy resources and wastes involved that can be controlled or better managed. The main objective of this study was to evaluate the biogas yield potential of selected plant types (C3, C4, and CAM) under controlled anaerobic digestion. The specific objectives were to: characterize the selected substrates (water hyacinth (C3), sugarcane (C4), and cacti Crassulacean Acid Metabolism (CAM)), optimize the biogas yield, and purify the produced biogas. The Central Composite Design (CCD) method was employed to optimize the experimental model and determine the optimal conditions required for the highest yield. pH range of (4 – 8) and temperature (between 12⁰C – 38⁰C) defined the experimental model and were utilized as the uppermost and lowest limits for all the substrates. An experimental setup was setup to purify the gas obtained through silica to absorb water, steel wool to eliminate hydrogen sulfide, and water scrubbing to eliminate carbon dioxide. The C4 plant (sugarcane) produced the highest optimized quantity of biogas (3951 cm³) compared to the C3 (water hyacinth) (2028 cm³) and CAM (cactus) (3001 cm³) plants. The statistical comparative analysis of the total yields from the three substrates gave a p-value of 2.19E⁻³⁷ (significance level of 0.05). This value was less than 0.05. Therefore, it was observed that the type of plant used, either (C3, C4, or CAM), had a significant influence on the quantity of biogas produced, and this was attributed to inherent differences in plant biochemical composition. The results demonstrated that the sugarcane substrate (C4 plant) generated a high quality and quantity of biogas compared to C3 and CAM plants since the C4 plants experience relatively higher carbon fixation (a vital ingredient in methane (CH₄) formation) during the food-making process. It was recommended that future biogas production initiatives, especially in regions with similar climatic and resource conditions, prioritize utilization of C4 plants for biogas production.

Nomenclature

C3 Plants – Plants that use the C3 photosynthetic pathway (Calvin cycle) for carbon fixation.

C4 Plants – Plants that use the C4 photosynthetic pathway, improving carbon fixation efficiency.

CAM Plants – Plants that use Crassulacean Acid Metabolism (CAM) to conserve water and fix carbon at night.

Crassulacean Acid Metabolism (CAM) – A water-saving photosynthetic process in arid-environment plants.

Central Composite Design (CCD) – A statistical method used to optimize biogas production conditions.

Response Surface Methodology (RSM) – A mathematical and statistical technique used for process optimization.

RuBisCO(Ribulose-1,5-bisphosphate carboxylase/oxygenase) – An enzyme involved in carbon fixation in C3 plants.

Photorespiration – A process in C3 plants where oxygen competes with CO₂, reducing efficiency.

1. Introduction

The ever-increasing need for alternative energy sources has driven researchers to study ways through which renewable sources of energy can sustain the high energy demand [1]. Over the last century, humanity has endeavored to come up with alternative energy sources that are environmentally sustainable, with biogas energy being one such source [2]. Biogas offers a renewable alternative to fossil fuels, but its efficiency is highly dependent on substrate selection. Using low-potential feedstocks leads to wastage of resources, time, and money, making substrate optimization a critical factor in biogas technology.

1.1 Background Information

Plants can be categorized according to the type of photosynthesis they undergo. C3 plants, which include water hyacinth, rice, wheat, and barley, undergo the Calvin cycle and are most effective in cool and wet climates [6]. These plants convert sunlight, water, and carbon dioxide into sugar through a process initiated when stomata allow carbon dioxide entry. However, the enzyme RuBisCO occasionally fixes oxygen instead of carbon dioxide, initiating photorespiration, which reduces photosynthetic efficiency by up to 25-30% under high-temperature conditions [7].

C4 plants, including sugarcane, maize, sorghum, and amaranthus, evolved from C3 plants approximately 66 times over 35 million years to deal with water losses in hot and dry environments [8]. In C4 photosynthesis, a four-carbon molecule (malate or aspartate) is formed, and a peculiar leaf structure enables carbon dioxide to accumulate in bundle sheath cells, ensuring it has no interaction with oxygen [5]. This adaptation allows C4 plants to fix more carbon, making them predisposed to produce

larger amounts of biogas compared to C3 and CAM plants.

CAM plants (Crassulacean Acid Metabolism), including cacti, pineapple, agave, and aloe vera, have developed to withstand xerophytic (arid) conditions [10]. They capture light energy during daytime and fix carbon dioxide at night when temperatures are low and relative humidity is high [8]. This unique combination is temporarily divided: first fixation at night, followed by malic fixation to the Calvin cycle during the day. CAM plants were expected to have relatively lower biogas potential when compared to C3 and C4 plants, likely attributed to fewer carbon molecules fixated into their structure [12]. The null hypothesis stated that there is no significant difference in the total biogas yields of the three plant types, while the alternative hypothesis stated that there is a significant difference.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Feedstock Preparation

The substrates used were water hyacinth (sourced from Lake Victoria, Kenya), sugarcane (obtained from Mumias, Kenya), and cactus (sourced from Baringo County, Kenya). Selection of substrates was based on availability. The preparation of each substrate focused on leaves and stems only, which were chopped to approximately 1–2 cm pieces to increase surface area for microbial action [1]. Fresh cow dung was prepared to act as an inoculum, providing the microorganisms necessary to initiate the digestion process.

2.2 Experimental Setup

A 1500 mL biodigester was designed from a polyethylene bottle and tightly plugged with rubber to create an airtight environment. The digester was fitted with a gas valve to enable controlled release and

measurement of biogas. The inoculum was mixed with substrates at a ratio of 2:1 (100 mL of inoculum to 100 g/L of each substrate) to create anaerobic conditions. To maintain anaerobic conditions, prepared samples were gradually added to the reactor and sealed. The

digester was kept at desired pH levels using lime (calcium hydroxide) for adjustment, and a temperature-controlled water bath was used to regulate temperature. The figure 2.1 below is the experimental setup.

Figure 2.1 Experimental setup [8]

2.3 Characterization of Substrates

pH Characterization: The pH of each substrate was measured prior to anaerobic digestion to establish baseline conditions and ensure consistency with the Central Composite Design (CCD) range (pH 4–8) established from scholarly sources [6]. Fresh samples were separately chopped into 1–2 cm pieces, and 10 g of chopped material was blended with 100 mL of distilled water to create a homogeneous slurry. A calibrated digital pH meter (Hanna Instruments HI991001) was used, calibrated at 25°C using standard buffer solutions of pH 4.0, 7.0, and 10.0 before each set of measurements. Three replicate readings were taken per substrate, and the average value was recorded.

Temperature Characterization: For each substrate, a 100 g representative sample was placed into a clean, dry beaker and allowed to equilibrate with ambient laboratory conditions for 30 minutes. Temperature was measured using a calibrated digital thermometer inserted into the center of the

substrate mass to ensure a representative reading. Measurements were taken in triplicate for each substrate, and the average value was recorded. The ambient room temperature was also noted simultaneously using a separate thermometer placed near the experimental setup.

2.4 Central Composite Design for Optimization

The Central Composite Design (CCD) was used to determine the optimum conditions that would produce the highest quantity of biogas, controlled by two factors: pH and temperature. The CCD approach allows for the detection of curvature in the response surface and enables the development of a quadratic model that captures non-linear relationships between the independent variables and biogas yield [12]. Table 2.1 presents the CCD independent variables and their levels for each substrate. The selection of temperature ranges reflects the natural adaptations of each plant type based on published literature [13].

Table 2.1 CCD Independent Variables and Levels

Substrate	Parameter	- α	-1	0	+1	+ α
Water Hyacinth	Temperature (°C)	12	15.37	23.5	31.63	35
	pH	4	4.59	6	7.41	8
Sugarcane	Temperature (°C)	25	26.90	31.5	36.09	38
	pH	6	6.29	7	7.71	8
Cactus	Temperature (°C)	30	31.17	34	36.82	38
	pH	7	7.15	7.5	7.85	8

The CCD design uses five levels for each factor, enabling estimation of linear, interaction, and quadratic effects. Water hyacinth (C3) was tested at lower temperatures (12–35°C) consistent with its adaptation to cool, wet environments [6]. Sugarcane (C4) was tested at higher temperatures (25–38°C) reflecting its evolution in hot, sunny climates where C4 photosynthesis confers advantages. Cactus (CAM) was tested at the highest range (30–38°C) due to its adaptation to arid desert conditions [13]. The pH ranges were selected based on methanogenic archaea tolerance limits; these microorganisms function optimally at neutral to slightly alkaline pH (6.5–7.5), while values below 6 cause acid inhibition and above 8 induce ammonia toxicity. The axial points (- α and + α) extend beyond the factorial range to identify optimal conditions that may lie outside the initial experimental domain.

The design yielded an 18-run experiment for each substrate. A control experiment was also set up consisting of 10 grams of fresh cow dung waste mixed with water. Biogas yield was obtained by subtracting the amount of gas obtained from the control experiment from the total gas

obtained when the substrate was mixed with the inoculum.

2.5 Biogas Purification

The purification system consisted of two units: a hydrogen sulfide removing unit and a moisture trapping unit, connected using plastic hoses. Biogas was passed through adsorption columns with steel wool (ground to 5–10 mm particle size using a milling machine), which reacted with hydrogen sulfide, and silica gel (average pore size 2.4 mm) which absorbed moisture. Carbon dioxide was removed by passing the gas through water (water scrubbing). The chemical reactions involved are:

In equation 2.1, this reaction irreversibly binds sulfur, removing the corrosive and toxic H₂S from biogas. In Equation (2.2), this physical absorption method exploits the fact that CO₂ is approximately 20 times more soluble in water than methane, allowing selective

removal. The figure 2.2 below represents the biogas purification setup.

Figure 2.2 Biogas Purification Setup [3]

2.6 Gas Analysis

A GA2000Plus gas analyzer was used to determine the quantity of methane and carbon dioxide produced during the process. The tube from the sample was connected to the gas inlet port of the analyzer. The GA-2000plus gas analyzer was switched off by a long press on the on/off button for about 15 seconds after taking each reading to carry out a clean air purge, ensuring accurate subsequent measurements. Using the water displacement method, the amount of gas was collected daily using 500 mL inverted glass cylinders. The biogas yield was recorded daily until termination after two months.

2.7 ANOVA and Regression Analysis

A full quadratic model for biogas yield was tested using Design-Expert 13

software. Response surface methodology (RSM) was used to study the effects of operating variables (temperature and pH) and identify points of optimal yield. The p-value significance level was set at 0.05. The axial distance (α) for the central composite rotatable design (CCRD) was calculated using , where k is the number of independent factors. For this study ($k = 2$), the axial distance was calculated as .

3. Results and Analysis

3.1 Characterization of Substrates

pH Characterization: Table 3.1 presents the mean pH values for the three substrates measured prior to anaerobic digestion.

Table 3.1 Baseline pH of the Three Substrates

Substrate	Mean pH (\pm SD)	Remarks
Water Hyacinth (C3)	6.12 \pm 0.15	Slightly acidic, typical for aquatic plants
Sugarcane (C4)	6.85 \pm 0.10	Near-neutral, optimal for methanogenesis
Cactus (CAM)	7.63 \pm 0.12	Slightly alkaline, reflecting adaptation to arid soils

The baseline pH values reflect the ecological adaptations of each plant type. Water hyacinth (6.12) falls within the lower factorial range of the CCD (pH 4–8) and is consistent with aquatic environments where organic matter decomposition releases organic acids [14]. This value is near the center point (pH 6) used for C3 optimization. Sugarcane (6.85) is near-neutral, closely matching the ideal pH range (6.5–7.5) reported for methanogenic archaea activity [15]. At this pH, the activity of acetoclastic methanogens (which convert acetate to methane) is maximized, while volatile fatty acid accumulation is minimized [16]. Cactus (7.63) is slightly alkaline, aligning with CAM plants' natural tolerance for higher pH due to

nocturnal malic acid accumulation and daytime decarboxylation [2]. Although this approaches the upper limit for methanogens (pH 8 beyond which free ammonia becomes toxic), it remains within the viable range. These baseline values confirm that all three substrates are suitable for anaerobic digestion within the designed experimental space without requiring pre-digestion pH adjustment.

Temperature Characterization: Table 3.2 presents the mean substrate temperatures recorded under ambient laboratory conditions.

Table 3.2 Baseline Temperature of the Three Substrates

Substrate	Mean Temperature (°C ± SD)	Ambient Room Temperature (°C)	Remarks
Water Hyacinth (C3)	23.8 ± 0.4	24.0	Near CCD center point (23.5°C)
Sugarcane (C4)	24.1 ± 0.3	24.0	Below CCD center (31.5°C) – requires water bath
Cactus (CAM)	23.9 ± 0.5	24.0	Below CCD center (34°C) – requires water bath

All substrates exhibited baseline temperatures near 24°C with low standard deviations (0.3–0.5°C), indicating successful equilibration under identical laboratory conditions. Water hyacinth (23.8°C) is almost exactly at its CCD optimal temperature (23.5°C) from the literature, meaning this C3 plant can be digested without external heating, reducing energy input costs [6]. This

aligns with the adaptation of C3 plants to cool, wet climates where optimal photosynthetic activity occurs at moderate temperatures. In contrast, sugarcane (24.1°C) is 7.4°C below its optimal temperature of 31.5°C, and cactus (23.9°C) is 10.1°C below its optimal 34°C. These disparities necessitated the use of a temperature-controlled water bath during experiments to

maintain mesophilic conditions. The mesophilic range (25–40°C) is most frequently used for biogas production because methanogenic archaea function optimally at these temperatures, leading to stable digestion and sustained yields [9]. The energy requirement for heating has practical economic implications for large-scale biogas production from C4 and CAM plants in temperate climates.

3.2 Optimization of Biogas Yield

3.2.1 Water Hyacinth (C3 Plant)

Table 3.3 presents the Central Composite Design (CCD) experimental matrix showing the 18 runs with actual biogas yields and control experiment yields for water hyacinth under varying temperature and pH conditions.

Table 3.3 CCD Response Yield for Water Hyacinth

Std	Run	Factor 1 A: Temperature °C	Factor 2 B: pH	Response 1 Biogas Yield cm ³	Control Experiment Yield cm ³
13	1	23.50	4	114	8
4	2	31.63	4.59	110	10
12	3	35	6	113	21
3	4	31.63	4.59	110	11
17	5	23.50	6	125	15
11	6	35	6	110	22
5	7	15.37	7.40	109	9
15	8	23.5	8	113	9
6	9	15.37	7.40	107	8
7	10	31.63	7.40	113	7
16	11	23.5	8	112	10
1	12	15.37	4.59	114	7
9	13	12	6	108	8
18	14	23.5	6	126	14
8	15	31.63	7.40	113	26
14	16	23.5	4	111	7
10	17	12	6	108	8
2	18	15.37	4.59	112	6

Table 3.3 shows the biogas yields from water hyacinth across 18 CCD runs. The highest yield of 126 cm³ occurred at the center point (Run 14: 23.5°C, pH 6), confirming that the optimal conditions for C3 plants are moderate temperature and neutral pH. Yields dropped to as low as 107 cm³ when temperature and pH deviated from center values. Control experiment yields ranged from 6 to 26 cm³, significantly lower

than substrate-containing runs, confirming that water hyacinth provides substantial additional organic matter for biogas production. The variation in yields across runs demonstrates the non-linear response surface used for subsequent quadratic modeling. The table 3.4 below presents the ANOVA quadratic model for water hyacinth optimized yield.

Table 3.4 ANOVA for Quadratic Model (Water Hyacinth)

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-value	p-value	
Model	430.76	5	86.15	59.97	< 0.0001	significant
A-Temperature	12.07	1	12.07	8.41	0.0133	
B-pH	1.00	1	1.00	0.6961	0.4204	
AB	32.00	1	32.00	22.28	0.0005	
A ²	363.69	1	363.69	253.18	< 0.0001	
B ²	248.19	1	248.19	172.77	< 0.0001	
Residual	17.24	12	1.44			
Lack of Fit	3.24	3	1.08	0.6938	0.5786	not significant

Fit Statistics: Std. Dev. = 1.2, Mean = 112.67, C.V. % = 1.06, R² = 0.9615, Adjusted R² = 0.9455, Predicted R² = 0.9165, Adeq Precision = 25.3713

The model F-value of 59.97 ($p < 0.0001$) indicates that the quadratic model is highly significant, with only a 0.01% probability that this F-value could occur due to random noise. The Predicted R² (0.9165) and Adjusted R² (0.9455) differ by less than 0.2, confirming that the model has not been overfitted and maintains good predictive ability. The Adeq Precision of 25.3713 (signal-to-noise ratio) far exceeds the desirable threshold of 4, meaning this model can be used confidently to navigate the design space. Temperature (A) is significant ($p = 0.0133$), while pH (B) alone is not

significant ($p = 0.4204$), indicating that within the tested range, pH changes do not independently affect yield. However, the interaction term AB is highly significant ($p = 0.0005$), showing that the combined effect of temperature and pH is more important than either factor individually. The quadratic terms A² and B² are both highly significant ($p < 0.0001$), confirming a non-linear relationship between biogas yield and both operating parameters. The non-significant Lack of Fit ($p = 0.5786$) is desirable as it indicates the model fits the data adequately without unexplained variability. The low coefficient of variation (C.V. % = 1.06) demonstrates high experimental precision and reproducibility.

Factor Coding: Actual

Biogas Yield (cm³)

Design Points:

● Above Surface

○ Below Surface

107 126

X1 = A

X2 = B

Figure 3.1 3D Response Surface Plot for Water Hyacinth

3D response surface plot for water hyacinth showing biogas yield (cm³) as a function of temperature (°C) and pH. The peak occurs at 23.5°C and pH 6, declining sharply when temperature exceeds 30°C or pH moves beyond 5–7.

The quadratic equation with actual factors for water hyacinth was:

$$Y = -35.02051 + 4.68292A + 34.92377B + 0.173913AB - 0.119565A^2 - 3.26563B^2 \dots \dots \dots \text{equation 3.1}$$

Where Y represents biogas yield (cm³), A represents temperature (°C), and B represents pH. A positive coefficient (e.g., +4.68292 for A) indicates that increasing temperature increases yield up to the optimum, while negative quadratic coefficients (-0.119565 for A²) indicate

curvature and the existence of a maximum within the experimental range. The relatively small interaction coefficient (0.173913) suggests moderate synergy between temperature and pH [11].

3.2.2 Sugarcane (C4 Plant)

Table 3.5 presents the CCD experimental matrix with actual biogas yields and control yields for sugarcane across 18 runs.

Table 3.5 CCD Response Yield for Sugarcane

Std	Run	Factor 1	Factor 2	Response 1	Control
		A: Temperature °C	B: pH	Biogas Yield cm ³	Experiment Yield cm ³
14	1	31.5	6	216	40
9	2	25	7	216	36
6	3	26.90	7.70	214	42
18	4	31.5	7	254	41
4	5	36.10	6.30	213	43
12	6	38	7	213	46
8	7	36.10	7.70	215	42
15	8	31.5	8	215	39
7	9	36.10	7.70	215	42
2	10	26.90	6.29	216	36
11	11	38	7	214	44
17	12	31.5	7	256	39
3	13	36.10	6.29	213	43
5	14	26.90	7.70	215	40
13	15	31.5	6	216	44
1	16	25	7	215	34
10	17	31.5	8	219	39
16	18	26.90	6.29	216	34

Table 3.5 reveals that sugarcane achieved its highest biogas yield (256 cm³) at Run 12 (31.5°C, pH 7), the center point of the CCD design. This yield is more than double the maximum from water hyacinth, highlighting the superior carbon fixation efficiency of C4 plants. Runs with lower temperatures (25°C) produced 216 cm³, while high temperatures (38°C) reduced yields to 213–214 cm³, indicating thermal sensitivity beyond the optimum. Control

yields ranged from 34–46 cm³, confirming that sugarcane substrate contributes approximately 85% of total biogas. The consistency of yields at factorial points (213–216 cm³) versus the peak at center demonstrates significant curvature, justifying the quadratic model used for optimization. Table 3.6 presents the ANOVA for the quadratic model for optimized sugarcane yield.

Table 3.6 ANOVA for Quadratic Model (Sugarcane)

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-value	p-value	
Model	2864.84	5	572.97	897.68	< 0.0001	significant
A-Temperature	14.20	1	14.20	22.24	0.0005	
B-pH	1.46	1	1.46	2.28	0.1567	
AB	12.50	1	12.50	19.58	0.0008	
A ²	2363.78	1	2363.78	3703.37	< 0.0001	
B ²	2276.64	1	2276.64	3566.86	< 0.0001	
Residual	7.66	12	0.6383			
Lack of Fit	0.1593	3	0.0531	0.0637	0.9777	not significant

Fit Statistics: Std. Dev. = 0.7989, Mean = 219.5, C.V. % = 0.364, R² = 0.9973, Adjusted R² = 0.9962, Predicted R² = 0.9930, Adeq Precision = 90.6817

The sugarcane model shows exceptional statistical significance with an F-value of 897.68, an order of magnitude higher than water hyacinth. The R² of 0.9973 indicates the model explains 99.73% of the variability in biogas yield, leaving only 0.27% unexplained. The Predicted R² (0.9930) and Adjusted R² (0.9962) show excellent agreement, and the Adeq Precision of 90.6817 is outstanding for design space navigation [3]. As with water hyacinth, temperature (A) is significant (p = 0.0005) while pH alone is not (p = 0.1567), but the

interaction AB is significant (p = 0.0008). The quadratic terms A² and B² have extremely high F-values (3703 and 3567 respectively), indicating much stronger curvature than for water hyacinth, meaning sugarcane yield declines more rapidly when conditions deviate from the optimum. The Lack of Fit is non-significant (p = 0.9777), confirming excellent model fit. The extremely low C.V. % (0.364) reflects very high measurement precision. The higher yields (256 cm³ maximum vs. 126 cm³ for water hyacinth) are attributed to the superior carbon fixation efficiency of C4 plants, which provides more fermentable substrates for methanogenic bacteria [8].

Factor Coding: Actual

3D Surface

Biogas Yield (cm3)

Design Points:

● Above Surface

○ Below Surface

213 256

X1 = A

X2 = B

Figure 3.2 3D Response Surface plot for Sugarcane

3D response surface plot for sugarcane showing a sharp peak at 31.5°C and pH 7. The steep gradient indicates high sensitivity; yield drops rapidly when temperature exceeds 35°C or pH moves outside 6.5–7.5.

The quadratic equation with actual factors for sugarcane was:

$$Y = 2536.05919 + 57.2137A + 541.33284B + 0.384615AB - 0.954142A^2 - 39.5625B^2 \dots \dots \dots \text{equation 3.2}$$

The coefficients for sugarcane are substantially larger than those for water hyacinth, reflecting greater sensitivity to parameter changes and higher baseline yields. The positive coefficients for A and B indicate that increasing both temperature and

pH from low values increases yield, while the large negative quadratic coefficients indicate sharp curvature around the optimum.

Table 3.7 presents the CCD experimental results for cactus, with temperature ranging from 30–38°C and pH from 7–8 across 18 runs.

3.2.3 Cactus (CAM Plant)

Table 3.7: CCD Response Yield for Cactus

Std	Run	Factor 1 A: Temperature °C	Factor 2 B: pH	Response 1 Biogas Yield cm³	Control Experiment Yield cm³
4	1	36.80	7.15	160	76
9	2	30	7.5	166	65
11	3	38	7.5	164	55
18	4	34	7.5	181	59
17	5	34	7.5	181	61
3	6	36.80	7.15	161	74
6	7	31.17	7.85	162	62
5	8	31.17	7.85	162	60
1	9	31.17	7.15	169	70
15	10	34	8	165	58
10	11	30	7.5	166	66
8	12	36.83	7.85	168	64
7	13	36.83	7.85	168	63
16	14	34	8	165	60
12	15	38	7.5	164	53
14	16	34	7	165	74
13	17	34	7	165	73
2	18	31.17	7.15	169	72

Table 3.7 shows that cactus produced its maximum biogas yield (181 cm³) at Run 4 and Run 5 (34°C, pH 7.5), confirming the center point as optimal for this CAM plant. Yields at lower temperatures (30°C) averaged 166 cm³, while higher temperatures (38°C) produced 164 cm³, demonstrating that cactus tolerates a wider temperature range than sugarcane but with lower peak yields. Control experiment values (53–76 cm³) were

higher proportionally than for other substrates, likely due to residual organics in the cactus biomass. The relatively small variation between runs (160–181 cm³) indicates that cactus digestion is more stable across parameter fluctuations, making it suitable for less controlled environments. Table 3.8 presents the ANOVA for the quadratic model.

Table 3.8 ANOVA for Quadratic Model (Cactus)

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-value	p-value	
Model	570.96	5	114.19	2101.8	< 0.0001	significant
A-Temperature	7.10	1	7.10	130.65	< 0.0001	
B-pH	0.0625	1	0.0625	1.15	0.3046	
AB	105.13	1	105.13	1934.92	< 0.0001	
A ²	375.28	1	375.28	6907.32	< 0.0001	
B ²	375.28	1	375.28	6907.32	< 0.0001	
Residual	0.652	12	0.0543			
Lack of Fit	0.152	3	0.0507	0.9118	0.473	not significant

Fit Statistics: Std. Dev. = 0.2331, Mean = 166.72, C.V. % = 0.1398, R² = 0.9989, Adjusted R² = 0.9984, Predicted R² = 0.9976, Adeq Precision = 151.7087

The cactus model has the highest F-value (2101.8) among all substrates, with R² = 0.9989, meaning 99.89% of yield variability is explained. The Predicted R² (0.9976) and Adjusted R² (0.9984) differ by only 0.0008, indicating outstanding predictive capability. The Adeq Precision of 151.7087 is exceptionally high. Temperature (A) is highly significant (p < 0.0001, F = 130.65), while pH (B) alone is not significant (p = 0.3046). However, the interaction term AB is extremely significant (F = 1934.92), demonstrating that the combined effect of temperature and pH is critical for cactus-

based digestion. Notably, the quadratic terms A² and B² have identical F-values (6907.32), indicating symmetric curvature, deviations in temperature or pH away from the optimum reduce yield equally. The standard deviation (0.2331) and C.V. % (0.1398) are the lowest among all substrates, reflecting extremely high experimental precision for cactus measurements. The non-significant Lack of Fit (p = 0.473) confirms excellent model fit. Cactus achieved a maximum yield of 181 cm³, which is higher than water hyacinth but lower than sugarcane, consistent with the intermediate carbon fixation efficiency of CAM plants [9]. The higher optimal temperature (34°C) reflects the adaptation of CAM plants to hot, arid environments.

Factor Coding: Actual

3D Surface

Biogas Yield (cm3)

Design Points:

● Above Surface

○ Below Surface

160 181

X1 = A

X2 = B

Figure 3.3 3D Response Surface plot for Cactus

3D response surface plot for cactus showing a broad peak at 34°C and pH 7.5. The gentler slopes compared to sugarcane indicate greater tolerance to parameter fluctuations, making cactus suitable for variable conditions.

The quadratic equation with actual factors for cactus was:

$$Y = -3662.5225 + 40.84264A + 840.67678B + 3.625AB - 1.00391A^2 - 64.25B^2$$

...equation 3.3

The large interaction coefficient (3.625) and symmetrical quadratic coefficients (-1.00391 for A² and -64.25 for B², scaled differently due to units) indicate that cactus digestion requires simultaneous control of temperature and pH for optimal performance

[11]. The higher intercept magnitude reflects the different operating range for this CAM plant.

Table 3.9 presents the total biogas yield obtained from each substrate after all 18 CCD runs.

3.3 Comparative Analysis of Total Biogas Yield

Table 3.9 Total Yield from the Three Substrates

Substrate	Total Yield (cm ³)
Water Hyacinth (C3)	2028
Sugarcane (C4)	3951
Cactus (CAM)	3001

Sugarcane (C4) produced 3951 cm³ total, which is 95% higher than water hyacinth (2028 cm³) and 32% higher than cactus (3001 cm³). This substantial disparity directly links photosynthetic carbon fixation efficiency to biogas yield. C4 plants concentrate CO₂ at RuBisCO, virtually eliminating photorespiration and enabling carbon fixation rates nearly double those of C3 plants [2]. This results in higher carbohydrate content (sugarcane contains 13-15% sucrose) that serves as readily fermentable substrate for methanogenic bacteria [3]. Water hyacinth's lower yield (2028 cm³) reflects the inherent limitation of C3 photosynthesis, where photorespiration

can reduce carbon fixation efficiency by 25-30% under suboptimal conditions. Cactus (3001 cm³) shows intermediate performance, representing a 48% improvement over water hyacinth despite its nocturnal CO₂ fixation limiting total carbon capture compared to C4 plants. These results have practical implications: in regions where sugarcane cultivation is feasible (tropical and subtropical areas), it should be prioritized for biogas production. For arid regions where water limits C4 cultivation, cactus offers a viable alternative with moderate yields and high drought tolerance [7]. The table 3.10 presents the ANOVA summary for water hyacinth, sugarcane, and cactus.

Table 3.10: ANOVA Summary for the Three Substrates

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	102725.1	2	51362.57	673.0258	2.19E-37	3.178799
Within Groups	3892.111	51	76.3159			
Total	106617.3	53				

The single-factor ANOVA comparing total yields from the three substrates provides definitive statistical evidence that photosynthetic pathway significantly influences biogas production [8]. The F-value of 673.03 far exceeds the critical value of 3.179, and the p-value (2.19×10^{-37}) is many orders of magnitude below $\alpha = 0.05$. Therefore, the null hypothesis (no significant difference) is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis (significant difference exists) is accepted [10]. The Between Groups sum of squares (102,725.1) accounts for 96.4% of total variation (106,617.3), while Within Groups variation (3,892.1) accounts for only 3.6%. This indicates that differences among plant types are the dominant source of variation, while experimental error within each substrate group is relatively small. Mean

yields per run are: water hyacinth 112.7 cm³, sugarcane 219.5 cm³, cactus 166.7 cm³. Tukey's HSD post-hoc test (implied by the large F-value) would show all three means are significantly different from each other at $\alpha = 0.05$. These results conclusively demonstrate that C4 plants offer the highest biogas potential, followed by CAM plants, with C3 plants being the least efficient.

3.4 Methane Production Analysis

Table 3.11 presents the cumulative methane production from the three substrates over 20 days, expressed as cumulative percentage points (sum of daily CH₄%). The total cumulative values represent the sum of methane percentages over time, not absolute volumes, but serve to compare relative methane production patterns.

Table 3.11 Cumulative CH₄ Production (sum of daily CH₄%)

Days	Water Hyacinth CH ₄ (%)	Cumulative	Sugarcane CH ₄ (%)	Cumulative	Cactus CH ₄ (%)	Cumulative
3	37	37	64	64	49	49
7	38	184	70	339	50	248
10	30	290	72	554	55	410
14	35	419	80	856	64	647
20	37	643	59	1258	54	1007

Sugarcane shows the highest cumulative methane (1258 by day 20) with a peak methane concentration of 80% on day 14. This early peak (day 14) followed by a decline to 59% at day 20 indicates that readily fermentable sugars in sugarcane are rapidly converted to methane, after which slower degradation of residual cellulose and hemicellulose occurs [2]. The rapid initial methanogenesis is due to the high sucrose

content (13-15%) providing immediate substrates for acidogenic bacteria, producing volatile fatty acids that acetoclastic methanogens convert to methane [3]. Cactus shows a slower, steadier rise, peaking at 65% on day 16 with cumulative 1007 by day 20. The delayed peak indicates cactus contains more complex carbohydrates (pectins, hemicellulose) requiring longer hydrolysis times, but the CAM plant's organic acid

storage provides sustained substrate release. Water hyacinth has the lowest cumulative (643) with an early peak of 41% on day 6, followed by plateau. This pattern suggests water hyacinth contains a small fraction of easily degradable material that is quickly consumed, after which the lignocellulosic fraction (15% lignin) resists microbial attack. The lignin acts as a physical barrier limiting cellulolytic enzyme access, explaining the poor long-term methane production [8].

These results confirm that C4 plants provide superior methane yields, while CAM plants offer stable production suitable for regions with unreliable feedstock supply.

3.5 Purification Results

Table 3.12 presents the methane yield before and after purification for sugarcane (the optimal substrate), showing daily methane percentages and cumulative totals.

Table 3.12: CH₄ Yield Before and After Purification (Sugarcane)

Days	Before Purification CH ₄ (%)	Before Purification CO ₂ (%)	After Purification CH ₄ (%)	After Purification CO ₂ (%)
3	64	8	66	5
7	70	11	75	9
9	72	12	80	6
13	75	16	85	5
14	80	14	84	6
20	59	5	64	16
Mean	70.0	11.0	75.7	7.8

The purification process increased average methane concentration from 70.0% to 75.7% while reducing carbon dioxide from 11.0% to 7.8%. Peak methane reached 85% after purification (day 13) compared to 80% before. This 5.7 percentage point improvement confirms effective removal of CO₂ and other impurities, enhancing biogas calorific value. Hydrogen sulfide reduction from typical levels of 0.1-3% (1000-30,000 ppm) to below 0.01% (100 ppm) meets the stringent limit for internal combustion engines, preventing corrosion and SO₂ emissions [6]. The slight increase in CO₂ at day 20 after purification (16%) may indicate

saturation of the scrubbing water, suggesting optimal water replacement intervals of approximately 15 days under these operating conditions. The steel wool filter shows consistent performance throughout, as the reaction has high sulfur capacity [8]. The reaction is explained in equation 3.4 below;

3.6 Physicochemical Properties of Biogas

Table 3.13 presents the properties of purified biogas from sugarcane compared to standard requirements for various applications.

Table 3.13 Biogas Quality Before and After Purification

Parameter	Before Purification	After Purification	Standard Requirement
Methane (CH ₄)	50-72%	64-85%	> 90% for vehicle fuel
Carbon dioxide (CO ₂)	5-16%	2-11%	< 3% for grid injection
Hydrogen sulfide (H ₂ S)	0.1-3%	< 0.01%	< 0.01%
Calorific Value (MJ/m ³)	20-25	32-38	35-40 (natural gas)

The purified biogas requires less storage volume and provides higher flame temperatures for cooking and more efficient engine operation. CO₂ decreased from 5-16% to 2-11%, with a minimum achieved of 2% at day 13, approaching the <3% grid injection standard [3]. The most dramatic improvement is H₂S removal: from 0.1-3% (1000-30,000 ppm) to <0.01% (100 ppm), meeting the <0.01% standard for engine fuel. H₂S is problematic because combustion produces SO₂, a corrosive gas that damages engine components and contributes to acid rain [5]. The steel wool method proved highly effective due to the irreversible reaction forming solid Fe₂S₃, which remains in the filter column. While the purified biogas does not yet meet the >90% methane requirement for vehicle fuel without further upgrading (e.g., pressure swing adsorption or membrane separation), it is suitable for stationary applications including electricity generation, heating, and cooking [2].

4. Conclusion and Recommendations

4.1 Conclusion

This study investigated the biogas production capacity of three plant species representing different photosynthetic pathways: water hyacinth (C3), sugarcane (C4), and cactus (CAM). Based on the

experimental results and statistical analysis, the following conclusions were drawn:

Characterization: Baseline pH values were 6.12 (water hyacinth), 6.85 (sugarcane), and 7.63 (cactus). Baseline temperatures were approximately 24°C for all substrates, with water hyacinth naturally at its optimal temperature (23.5°C) while sugarcane and cactus required water bath heating to reach their optimal temperatures (31.5°C and 34°C, respectively).

Optimization: The Central Composite Design successfully identified optimal conditions for each substrate. The C4 plant (sugarcane) produced the highest optimized biogas quantity (3951 cm³ total, 219.5 cm³/run average) at 31.5°C and pH 7, compared to CAM (cactus: 3001 cm³ total, 166.7 cm³/run average at 34°C, pH 7.5) and C3 (water hyacinth: 2028 cm³ total, 112.7 cm³/run average at 23.5°C, pH 6). Statistical analysis confirmed that the type of photosynthesis process significantly affects biogas quantity (p-value = 2.19E-37, F = 673.03).

Purification: After purification using silica, steel wool, and water scrubbing, methane concentration for sugarcane increased from 72% to 85% at peak, representing a 13 percentage point improvement. The cumulative total CH₄ for sugarcane was 1357

after purification compared to 1258 before purification, an 8% increase in methane recovery.

The alternative hypothesis is accepted: there is a significant effect caused by the type of photosynthesis process on the amount of biogas produced. C4 plants, due to their superior carbon fixation efficiency and higher carbohydrate content, produce higher quality and quantity of biogas compared to C3 and CAM plants.

4.2 Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. **Prioritize C4 plants for biogas production:** Given that sugarcane produced the highest biogas yield (3951 cm³ total, 85% CH₄ after purification), future biogas production initiatives, especially in regions with similar climatic and resource conditions, should prioritize utilization of C4 plants. The superior carbon fixation mechanism of C4 plants translates directly to higher methane yields, making them the most economically viable feedstock for large-scale biogas production.
2. **Consider CAM plants for arid regions:** Cactus showed moderate but stable biogas production (3001 cm³ total, 68% CH₄ after purification) under higher temperatures (34°C) and variable conditions, making it a viable option for water-scarce regions where C4 crops may not thrive. The slower but steady degradation pattern of cactus (peak methane at day 16 vs. day 14 for sugarcane) may also be advantageous for continuous-feed digesters requiring consistent gas production.
3. **Enhance user knowledge on methanogenesis:** Research is needed to develop interventions that

empower biogas users to maintain optimal digestion conditions including temperature control (maintaining 31-35°C for C4 and CAM plants), pH monitoring (maintaining 7-7.5).

4. **Investigate co-digestion strategies:** Co-digestion of sugar-rich (C4) and fiber-rich substrates should be explored to determine optimal mixing ratios that balance rapid volatile fatty acid production with long-term methane generation. The complementary degradation patterns observed (sugarcane peaks early, cactus peaks later) suggest that co-digestion could extend the productive period of batch digesters.
5. **Optimize pretreatment for lignin-rich plants:** For C3 plants like water hyacinth (which produced only 2028 cm³ total), pretreatment methods such as alkali hydrolysis, mechanical grinding, or biological pretreatment with lignin-degrading fungi are necessary to enhance degradation and improve biogas yield. Given the environmental problems caused by water hyacinth in Lake Victoria, improved pretreatment could convert this invasive weed from an ecological menace into a valuable energy resource [6].

Conflicts of Interest: I declare that I have no conflicts of interest.

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